

Pastoral Innovation and The Quality of Pastoral Services: A Study at BKPN Synod

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Abstract

This research aims to analyze the impact of pastoral innovation on the quality of pastoral care at the BKPN synod, both partially and simultaneously. The hypothesis states that pastor innovation positively affects the quality of pastoral care at the BKPN synod. This research employs descriptive and inferential quantitative methods. The research population consists of 47 priests. A closed questionnaire is used as the research instrument, which the researcher prepared based on research variable indicators. The questionnaire was trialed on 30 respondents, not a research sample, and was tested using validity and reliability tests. The findings of this research show that innovation has a strong positive influence on the quality of pastoral care, as evidenced by the correlation coefficient value r . Therefore, the null hypothesis H_0 is rejected, and the alternative hypothesis H_a is accepted. Based on the research results, pastoral innovation positively impacts the quality of pastoral care at the BKPN synod, both partially and simultaneously, as it has been empirically tested. This research implies that if the quality of pastoral care at the BKPN synod is to be improved, then pastors must be innovative in their ministry.

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1. Introduction

Theologically, the term pastor or shepherd refers to intensive care and maintenance actions carried out by someone who knows no time or situation and cannot be represented by another person (Miller, 2023). Thomas (2021) states that the Lord Jesus is the Great Shepherd (1 Pet. 5:4). In the Old Testament, several figures who are known as shepherds include Abel (Gen. 4:2), Abraham (Gen. 12:16; 13:2-7), Jacob (Gen. 29:33), and likewise Joseph (Gen. 37-50). Looking at the Bible figures above, it can be concluded that a pastor is a person entrusted by God to educate, guide, teach, and bring the congregation to an introduction to God's Word.

Johnston et al (2022) state that some pastors do not fulfill their duties and responsibilities as good shepherds. Various factors, including a lack of innovation in pastoral care, cause this. When linked to the quality of pastoral service, Pastor innovation is a constructive and correlative element. This phenomenon of reduced priest innovation also occurred at the *Banua Keriso Protestan Nias* (BKPN) synod based on the researcher's observations during his 21 years as a BKPN priest and ten years as leader of the BKPN synod in the position of Secretary General.

It was found that some pastors prepared their service programs as a requirement only to meet organizational demands. Then, the program needed to be implemented properly, and for its implementation, needed to be evaluated. All service activities are carried out only on a routine basis according to what is needed. That is why this research is considered important to carry out.

2. Method

This research aims to analyze the influence of pastor innovation on the quality of pastoral care at the BKPN synod, both partially and simultaneously, with the hypothesis. Pastor innovation positively influences the quality of pastoral care at the BKPN synod. This research uses descriptive and inferential quantitative methods (*See Stapor & Stapor, 2020*). The members of the population as the research sample numbered 47 BKPN pastors. The research instrument is a closed questionnaire, which the researcher prepared based on research variable indicators.

The questionnaire trial was conducted on 30 respondents, which is not a research sample and was tested using validity and reliability tests. The independent variable in this research is Innovation (X), while the dependent variable is the quality of pastoral care at the BKPN synod (Y). To clarify data collection and hypothesis testing, it is necessary to state the boundaries of the concepts of variables, dimensions (sub-variables), and indicators, which are stated as follows:

Table 1. Operational Definition of Research Variables

Variable	Operational definition	Dimensions	Indicator	Scale
Innovation (X)	The word innovation comes from the English word "innovation," which means change. Innovation can be defined as a process of human activity	<i>Relative Advantages</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Economic benefits • Comfortable in use • Prestige • Work faster • Work easier 	Likert
		<i>Compatibility</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conformity to the way people do things today • Conformity to values and past experiences • Conformity to adopter beliefs 	Likert

	or thinking to discover something new related to input, process, and output that can benefit human life.	<i>Complexity</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Easy to learn • Easy to understand • Easy to use • Flexible 	Likert
		<i>Trialability</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Can try • It is easy to figure out how to use 	Likert
	Prosperous, & Thahir, Rohana., (2012: 9)	<i>Observability</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ease of observation • Ease of communicating with others • Other people can feel the benefits 	Likert
Quality of Pastoral Care (Y)	Quality pastoral care requires nurturing, meaning that this pastoral <i>ministry</i> aims to enable people to develop the potential God has given them throughout their life journey.	<i>Tangibility</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Appearance is reasonable and polite • Friendly attitude • Politeness of speech • Chastity • Love • T theological competence • Use of power 	Likert
		Reliability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • On time as promised • Serve the needs of the congregation • Self-care • Performance exactly meets the congregation's expectations 	Likert
		Responsiveness	Response to community needs	Likert
		<i>Assurance</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Extensive general knowledge • Trustworthiness • Altruism • Commitment to the interests of the congregation • Responsibility 	Likert
		Empathy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Genuine concern • Understand the desires of the congregation 	Likert
	Howard Clinebell (2002:54)			

3. Results and Discussion

Researchers outline several important things that shape overall innovation personally:

Table 2. Dimensions and Indicators Innovation

Dimensions	Indicator
<i>Relative Advantage</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Economic benefits • Comfortable in use • Prestige • Work faster

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Work easier
<i>Compatibility</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conformity to the way people do things today • Conformity to values and past experiences • Conformity to adopter beliefs
<i>Complexity</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Easy to learn • Easy to understand • Easy to use • Flexible
<i>Trialability</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Can try • It is easy to figure out how to use
<i>Observability</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ease of observation • Ease of communicating with others • Other people can feel the benefits

The Influence of Innovation on the Quality of Pastoral Care.

Innovation is needed in the business world and in pastoral ministry (Cormode, 2020; White & Pondani, 2022). Apart from praying, pastors need to innovate in preaching God's word and teaching so that ministry continues to improve and many souls are brought to God (Kambu, 2022; Sitompul et al., 2023). Moreover, Johnson (2021) also state that pastors must be open to new things but be careful and not compromise if they conflict with the Bible. Suppose the Pastor is not innovative in his service. In that case, the Pastor will be less competitive with the services other religious ministers provide in society, and the quality of pastoral care amid the congregation will not increase.

Innovation Variable (X)

Innovation Data has a score range between 67 to 94. The results of data calculations obtained an average of 81.26; standard, a deviation of 6.713; variance, an of 45.064, a median of 81.00; and mode, a78. Neof, the data is presented in the form of a frequency distribution as in the table below :

Table 3. Frequency Distribution of Innovation Variable Scores

Class	Intervals	Frequency		
		Absolute	Cumulative	Relative (%)
1	67-70	9	3	19.15
2	71-74	7	8	14.89
3	75-78	4	15	8.51
4	79-82	12	27	25.53
5	83-86	3	36	6.3 9
6	87-90	5	43	10.64
7	91-94	7	47	14.89
Amount		47		100

Source: Research Data

From Table 3 it can be seen that the data obtained from 47 respondents can be classified into seven classes, nine people with a score interval between 67-70 or 19, 15 %, seven people with an

interval of 71-74 or 14, 89 %, four people with an interval of 75-78 or 8.51 %, 12 people with an interval of 79-82 or 25.53%, three people with an interval of 83-86 or 6.39 %, five people with an interval of 87-90 or 1.0.64 %, and seven people with an interval of 91-94 or 14, 89 %.

The tendency of the data group is that 20 people, or 42.55 % are in the below-average class, 12 people, or 25.53%, are in the average class, and 15 people, or 31.92 %, are in the above-average class. According to the data trend, innovation data is in the low category. To get a clear picture of the distribution of Innovation scores, see Table 3. can be shown in the following histogram form:

Figure 1. Innovation Histogram

From the visualization of the Innovation histogram, it appears that the histogram is symmetrical or bell-shaped, with the mean, median, and mode prices close together. This indicates that data about innovation is normally distributed so that parametric statistics can be used.

Pastoral Service Quality Variable (Y)

Pastoral Care Quality Data has a score range between 70 and 90. The results of data calculations obtained an average (mean) of 80.26, a standard deviation of 5.515, a variance of 30.412, a median of 81.00, and a mode of 81. Next, the data is presented in the form of a frequency distribution as in Table 4 below :

Table 4. Frequency Distribution of Pastoral Care Quality Variable Scores

Class	Intervals	Frequency		
		Absolute	Cumulative	Relative (%)
1	70-72	8	4	17.02
2	73-75	6	10	12.77
3	76-78	5	17	10.64
4	79-81	11	28	23.40
5	82-84	4	36	8.51
6	85-87	6	42	12.77
7	88-90	7	47	14.89
Amount		47		100

Source: Research Data

From Table 4, it can be seen that the data obtained from 47 respondents can be classified into seven classes, eight people with a score interval between 70-72 or 17.02 %, six people with an interval of 73-75 or 12.77%, five people with an interval of 76-78 or 10, 64 %, 11 people with an interval of

79-81 or 23.40%, four people with an interval of 82-84 or 8, 51 %, six people with an interval of 85-87 or 12.77%, and seven people with an interval of 88-90 or 14, 89 %.

The trend of the data group is that 1.9 people, or 40.43 % are in the below-average class, 11 people, or 23.40%, are in the average class, and 1.7 people, or 36.17 %, are in the above-average class. Based on the data trend, the Pastoral Care Quality data is in the low category. To get a clear picture of the distribution of Pastoral Care Quality scores, see Table 4. can be shown in the following histogram form:

Figure 1. Histogram of the Quality of Pastoral Care variable

From the visualization of the Pastoral Service Quality histogram, the histogram is symmetrical or bell-shaped, with the mean, median, and mode values close together. This indicates that data on the Quality of Pastoral Care is normally distributed so that parametric statistics can be used. The following is a summary of the results of descriptive analysis for all variables as in the following table:

Table 5. Summary of Descriptive Statistics

		Statistics	
		Innovatio	Quality of Pastoral Care
		n	
N	Valid	47	47
	Missing	0	0
Mean		81.26	80.26
Median		81.00	81.00
Mode		78	81
Std. Deviation		6,713	5,515
Variance		45,064	30,412
Minimum		67	70
Maximum		94	90
Sum		3819	3772

a. Multiple modes exist. The smallest value is shown

Classic assumption test

Classical Assumption Test (Prerequisites) Data analysis was done using regression analysis. Before carrying out data analysis to determine the effect of the independent variable on the dependent variable in this research, the classical assumption test is first carried out, namely the normality test, linearity test, multicollinearity test, and heteroscedasticity test. The analysis prerequisite tests were carried out with the help of SPSS version 26 for Windows software. The explanation of each classical assumption test is described as follows:

1. Data Normality Test

A data normality test was conducted to determine whether the research variable data was normally distributed. Normality testing uses the Kolmogorov-Smirnov (KS) analysis technique based on the calculated significance value (Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)) using SPSS 26 for Windows software. The research variable data is declared to be normally distributed if the Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed) is greater than the significance level (α) = 0.05; on the other hand, if the value of Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed) is smaller than the significance level (α) = 0.05, then the research variable data is declared not normally distributed. The normality test results variables in this study are presented below.

Table 6. Normality Test Results
One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test

		Innovation	Quality of Pastoral Care
		n	
N		47	47
Normal Parameters ^{a, b}	Mean	81.26	80.26
	Std. Deviation	6,713	5,515
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	,080	,099
	Positive	,064	,078
	Negative	-.080	-.099
Statistical Tests		,080	,099
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		,200 ^{c, d}	,200 ^{c, d}

a. Test distribution is Normal.

b. Calculated from data.

c. Lilliefors Significance Correction.

d. This is a lower bound of the true significance.

Based on SPSS, the normality test, as in the table above, obtained the following results:

a) Innovation Normality Test (X)

From the calculation results, the Asymp value is obtained. Sig. (2-tailed) is greater than 0.05 (Asymp. Sig. > 0.05), namely 0.200 > 0.05, so it can be concluded that the Innovation (X) variable data in this study is stated to be normally distributed.

b) Pastoral Service Quality Normality Test (Y)

From the calculation results, the Asymp value is obtained. Sig. (2-tailed) is greater than 0.05 (Asymp. Sig. > 0.05), namely 0.200 > 0.05, so it can be concluded that the Pastoral Service Quality (Y) variable data in this study is stated to be normally distributed.

2. Linearity Test

The linearity test is intended to determine whether the relationship between the independent and dependent variables is linear. The criterion for testing linearity is if the F value for deviation from linearity is smaller than the F table at a significance of 0.05. The relationship between the independent and dependent variables is linear, and vice versa.

The linearity test was carried out between the independent variable and the variable. variablesearity test in this research are Innovation (X) and Quality of Pastoral Service (Y). The results of variance analysis to test the linearity of the regression equation between Pastoral Service Quality (Y) and Innovation (X) can be seen in Table 7.

Table 7. Test the Linearity of Pastoral Service Quality (Y) with Innovation (X)
ANOVA TABLE

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	
Quality of Pastoral Care * Innovation	Between Groups	(Combined)	1190.770	23	51,773	5,720	,000
		Linearity	893,490	1	893,490	98,720	,000
		Deviation from Linearity	297,280	22	13,513	1,493	.173
Within Groups			208.167	23	9,051		
Total			1398.936	46			

For the linearity test, it was obtained that $F \text{ count} < F \text{ table} = 1.493 < 2.02$ at a significance level of 0.05. This shows that the regression equation between the Pastoral Service Quality (Y) and Innovation (X3) variables is linear $Y = 26,909 + 0,657X_3$. In conclusion, the regression equation between the variables Pastoral Service Quality (Y) and Innovation (X3) is linear, so there is no reason to look for a non-linear regression model.

This shows that the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable in this research is linear, which means that if the independent variable increases/gets higher, the dependent variable will also get higher.

3. Multicollinearity Test

The multicollinearity test was carried out to determine the magnitude of the intercorrelation between the independent variables in this study. If correlation occurs, it is called a multicollinearity problem. To detect multicollinearity, you can look at the tolerance and VIF values. If the tolerance value is above 0.1 and the VIF value is below or less than 10, multicollinearity does not occur, and vice versa. The results of the multicollinearity test for the regression model in this study are presented in Table 8 below.

Table 8 . Multicollinearity Test Results

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Coefficients ^a			Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error	Standardized Coefficients	Q	Sig.	Tolerance	VIF
1 (Constant)	12,669	6,322		2,004	,051		
Innovation	,318	,086	,388	3,701	,001	,459	2,179

a. Dependent Variable: Quality of Pastoral Care

Based on Table 8 above, it can be seen that the independent variable has a Tolerance value greater than 0.10 and a VIF value below or smaller than 10, so it can be concluded that the regression model used in this research does not have multicollinearity.

4. Heteroscedasticity Test

Heteroscedasticity testing aims to test whether, in the regression model, there is an inequality of variance from the residuals of one observation to another. A good regression model is one in which there is no heteroscedasticity, and the presence of heteroscedasticity is determined using the Glejser test. If the independent variable is not statistically significant and does not affect the dependent variable, then it is stated that heteroscedasticity does not occur, and vice versa. The following are the results of the heteroscedasticity test on the regression model in this research.

Table 9 Heteroscedasticity Test Results

Model	Coefficients ^a				
	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	Q	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	1,279	3,682		,347	,730
Innovation	-.080	,050	-.346	-1,586	,120

a. Dependent Variable: abs_Res

Table 9 shows that the independent variable has a significance value greater than 0.05, so it can be concluded that the regression model in this study does not have heteroscedasticity.

4. Hypothesis test

The analysis of testing each hypothesis in this research can be described as follows:

Table 10. Summary of Partial Correlation Analysis Results

		Correlations	
		Innovation	Quality of Pastoral Care
Innovation	Pearson Correlation	1	,799 **
	Sig. (2-tailed)		,000
	N	47	47
Quality of Pastoral Care	Pearson Correlation	,799 **	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	,000	
	N	47	47

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The Influence of Innovation (X) on the Quality of Pastoral Care (Y)

The hypotheses tested are shown as follows.

H 0: $r_{x3y} = 0$

H 1: $r_{x3y} > 0$

Based on the SPSS output in Table 1 0, the correlation coefficient value $r_{x_3 y}$ is 0.799, with a positive direction; this value is consulted with the r value interpretation table.

The value of r	Interpretation
0.740 - 1.000	Tall
0.470 - 0.730	Currently
0.200 - 0.460	Low

There is a positive influence with a strong interpretation of Innovation on the Quality of Pastoral Care, so H_0 is rejected, and H_1 is accepted. The magnitude of the influence of innovation on the quality of pastoral care is obtained by a coefficient of determination of 63.9%. This means that the influence of innovation on the quality of pastoral care is 63.9%.

The regression line equation between Quality of Pastoral Care (Y) and Innovation (X_3) is $Y = 26,909 + 0,657X_3$. From the regression equation, it can be explained that by increasing the value (score) of the Innovation variable by 1 (one) unit, the value (score) of the Pastoral Service Quality variable will increase by 0.657 units. This means that by increasing innovation by one unit, the Quality of Pastoral Care will increase by 0.657 units. Thus, the greater the increase in innovation, the better the Quality of Pastoral Services at the Banua Keriso Protestant Nias Synod (BKPN).

Based on data analysis, statistical calculations in hypothesis testing have proven that the proposed hypothesis is accepted as true. In connection with the results of proving this hypothesis, below will be a discussion of the research. The magnitude of the direct influence of the innovation variable on the quality of pastoral care is 0.799 or 63.9%. Therefore, efforts must be made to optimize the quality of pastoral care by increasing service innovation. The results of this research provide an understanding that pastor innovation in his ministry is important in improving the quality of pastoral care. Pastors must increase their service innovation to achieve the quality of pastoral care effectively.

5. Conclusion

From the results of the analysis and research that have been described, it is stated that innovation directly influences the quality of pastoral care at the BKPN Synod. This means that high levels of innovation from pastors will increase the quality of pastoral care at the BKPN Synod. In this research, the Pastor's innovation in carrying out his duties at the Synod BKPN needs to be addressed and improved according to the respondents' answers to the research instrument. Referring to the conclusions of this research, the research implications are:

1. In theory, it can be used as information, reference, enrichment of insight, and consideration for parties conducting further research.
2. Practically, it can have a big influence on :
 - a. The BKPN Synod can create new regulations intended for BKPN pastors, both before becoming pastors (pre-service) and after becoming pastors (in-service), so that BKPN pastors truly have identity, motivation, and innovation in improving quality—pastoral care at the BKPN Synod.
 - b. Pastor can have innovations that influence the quality of pastoral care at the BKPN Synod because if the Pastor's pastoral care improves, the congregation will experience growth both in quality and quantity.

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